

Role of Data Science in Carbon Capture

Study of different Machine learning based approach assisting the fight against climate change

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Background

According to the COP21 Paris summit, a Major threat against the future well being of planet earth is Climate change. Also known as Paris agreement, it is a legally binding international treaty on climate change. Reaching to a common agreement between 195 countries in itself is a big achievement, but only agreeing won't solve the actual problem, rather numerous actions needs to be taken in order to reduce the carbon footprints. This Abstract highlights the role of Data science in capturing Carbon and thereby assisting in the mitigation of climate change.

The studies of using data science for carbon capture exists as scattered in literature. Only few attempts have been made towards reconciliation. This Abstract reviews those literatures and focuses on the role of data science in capturing carbon while keeping utilization and storage of captured carbon, out of scope.

Figure 1: Smart Carbon Capture[1]

As shown in Figure 1, the main objective of carbon capture process is to efficiently separate carbon from the mixture of gases (O₂, N₂, CO₂, etc.). Efficiently here means minimizing the energy and costs required for the whole process. Advancement in data science, especially in machine learning and deep learning has a huge impact in the field of natural sciences [2] visible from its applications in chemistry, physics and material sciences[3]. An emerging use of

machine learning techniques for carbon capture is observed in literature[4][5].

KEYWORDS

Carbon capture, data science, thermodynamics, climate change

METHODS

According to Rahimi Et. al there are two types of carbon capture processes, Absorption based and adsorption based. Rahimi Et. al explores both the process at molecular as well as process levels whereas Yan Yongliang Et. al explores in addition to absorption and adsorption based capture process the oxy-fuel and chemical-looping combustion process. **Machine learning in Absorption process:** Here, the main aim of machine learning is to predict the thermodynamic properties of the CO₂-absorbent system. The modelling and simulation of solvent based carbon capture is intensive and time consuming [6] as it includes mass transfer and chemical reactions for both liquid and gas phases. Common approach in modelling such absorption process includes equilibrium and non-equilibrium stage models. Former contain a set of equations known as MESH equations (Mass balance, Equilibrium, summation and Enthalpy) whereas later contains MERQ equations (Material balance, Energy balance, Rate and Equilibrium). In addition to these equations a number of other factors like physical properties and transport properties such as viscosity, heat and mass transfer coefficients, thermal conductivity, density, etc. have to be considered. This makes simulation modelling even more complicated and error prone.

In contrast, Machine learning methods such as ANN, ANFIS, SVR, RBF, and GP can predict the target with acceptable accuracy [6] Target in this case is usually the CO₂ Capture levels and rate of absorption of CO₂

Amines are the most frequently used absorbent for carbon capture process having capture capacity of around 85 to 90% [7]. ML Models can predict the CO₂ solubility of CO₂ Amine systems. Alternative to Amines, ILs are also used as absorbing agent because of their low vapor pressure, high thermal stability, and structure tunability. [8]

Considering the general property of ILs, features such as molecular weights, critical pressure and temperature are used as input parameters by a machine learning model.

Figure 2: Input features to predict CO₂ solubility[1]

[6] reviews the ML based process modelling and optimization techniques, ML based thermodynamic modelling studies, ML based property modelling studies. It also explores the ML based models that are used for solvent selection and design. Comparing the ML based approach to the traditional mathematical and property models, [6] concludes that the ML models are more accurate as they provide a complex and non-linear relationship between the inputs and the outputs. **Machine learning in Adsorption process:** Adsorption based carbon capture involves the selection of the best solid adsorbent. This selection ranges from traditional Zeolites to novel porous materials used as adsorbents. As [6] mentions there exists large databases over one million of real and in silico hypothetical porous structures that are available to designers. Because of the complexity and a wide range of selection materials, data science solution is not enough rather a combined solution of data science and big data is required. Other than adsorbent selection, synthesizability, stability to moisture, life cycle costs, thermal properties etc. should also be considered. [1] presents a schematic of several steps involved to systematically design ML based adsorption based carbon capture techniques. After the selection of Adsorbents, it is also important to evaluate the performance of the material in carbon capture, out of all possible combinations, the best selected / predicted material needs then to be synthesized.

Figure 3: ML implementation for Adsorption based carbon capture[1]

Results

The reviewed literature summarizes the application of data science in capturing CO₂. For both absorption as well adsorption based capture process, extensive use of ML based approach are evident. It is used as a valuable tool to predict the thermodynamic properties of CO₂, solubility of absorbents, adsorbent selection, process modelling and optimization. Many machine learning algorithms are also used at process level to model entire carbon capture plants. It should be noted that ML being a data driven tool, the quality of data used is highly important. Literature shows that the data used for training purpose is extensively obtained either from experiments or computational simulations. In that case it becomes very important to evaluate the ranges and conditions under which the simulations took place represents the actual process.

Conclusion

Based on literature reviewed in this abstract it could be concluded that the use of Data Science is evident in carbon capture process. It is not only at an experiment stage rather looking at the complexity of the problem, ML based solutions outperforms traditional modelling and optimization approach. The data quality still remains the prime focus, it should also be noted that the ML models are robust in training data range, hence overtraining must be taken care of. It should not be forgotten that the main aim of capturing carbon is reducing the carbon footprints. Although a data science solution enhances the capturing potential but it is of no use if the energy required for processing those big data solutions leaves lots of Carbon footprints behind. A study from [9] shows that the current IT infrastructure is a material contributor to global carbon emissions. Huge data centers around the world contribute two percent of total human carbon output, roughly equivalent to the airline industry. Of course not all the data centers are dedicated towards performing data science, still it is important that improving carbon capture must not equally contribute to the carbon emissions.

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